

Elements of Social Well Being in the Pluralism of Jain Logic

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Introduction

The present discourse on national development and prosperity has gone much beyond than simple socio-economic parameters and has been taking into account factors like harmony among various groups, stability in the society as well as inclusion of each and every one for betterment. In short, no country can provide prosperity and happiness to its people if there is a lack social well-being. The same applies to the global scenario where global peace and cooperation have become vital for the humankind.

The harsh reality which the world faces right now is the deterioration of social well-being and harmony at every level. Rapid changes in the social patterns of human civilization have caused several repercussions due to which, social well-being of people is diminishing- something everyone will agree to.

The Jain logic which is based upon the central philosophy of Anekanta and its subsets including Syadvada, Saptbhanginaya and Nayavada; provides us an alternative approach towards handling conflicts and difficult situations and maintaining our social well-being. The pluralistic approach of Jain logic due to its relative nature is the need of the hour in the present day world where thoughts, ideologies and institutions are at a constant clash.

Through its ideas of relative truth, co-existence of multiple worldviews and plural nature of realities; Jain logic is capable of providing us solutions for the modern day socio-civilizational problems and leading us to social well-being. Therefore, this paper will focus on five aspects of Jain logic that are relevant for modern social well-being namely- Conflict Resolution through a counter view to Ethnocentrism, Multiplicity of Worldviews, the Idea of Co-existence, Counter to One-Sided Viewpoints and Importance of Every Opinion. The paper will

attempt to analyse these five aspects by applying the central philosophy of Anekanta and its methodology of Syadvada and will ultimately present their relevance in the modern social system.

Resolving Conflicts: Counter View to Ethnocentrism

The human society is an ever-evolving institution which has seen rapid as well as drastic changes in the last few decades as the result of several factors working together. The society today is becoming more complex, globalised as well as increasingly cosmopolitan in nature. The advancements in socio-political freedoms have also enhanced individual rights altering the dynamics of every country and society. At the same time, these developments bring their own challenges. Growths of factors like cosmopolitanism and individual rights have also led to rise in conflicts within the society. A major cause of conflicts is the clash of viewpoints and ideologies which are present in the same social landscape. Unfortunately, these differences in thoughts and opinions are becoming ever hostile with time.

One of the several problematic issues responsible for hostile clash of ideologies is Ethnocentrism. Indiana University identifies Ethnocentrism as-

“One common mistake that people from all cultures are guilty of is Ethnocentrism- placing one’s own culture and corresponding beliefs, values and behaviors in the center. When we do this, we view our position as normal and right and evaluate all other cultural systems against our own.”

In the core of Ethnocentrism lay the same issues of non-acceptance of other viewpoints and absolutist tendency regarding one’s own ideas. This phenomenon should also be seen at the individual level at which people are becoming adamant about their thought systems. The Jain logic through its principles of multi-faceted reality and presence of innumerable aspects of truth; provides an efficient refutation for the ethnocentric view. The doctrine of ‘Naya’ accepts the presence of relative truth in every viewpoint, leading us to notions of relativity and refuting absolutism.

The Jain logic provides solutions for ethnocentrism through the inherent receptiveness in its worldview resulted by the ideas of relative truth and pluralism. It advocates for constant engagement and exchange of thoughts against Ethnocentrism which believes only its cultural worldview to be right. Sutrakritanga says the following about those who do not engage in arguments and discourse-

“Thus some (wrong philosophers) do not apply to others for arguments, but they continue to err because they believe that their own arguments are right”

Hence, every culture and belief system must be open to positive engagement as propounded by the Jain logic which is the only effective way to counter Ethnocentrism. This spirit of engagement is further seen in the same text where ideological chauvinism is condemned by the following sutra-

“Some say that they will be perfected and sound. On the head of Perfection some men are infatuated with their own doctrines.”

The Jain doctrine of ‘Naya’ accepts the possibility of presence of reality in every statement. Hemchandra points out to this plurality of truth in his work ‘Anyayoga-Vyavachheda-Dvatrinshika’ and says that Reality is possessed of innumerable characters, it is not possible to explain it any other way.

Hence, one is expected to engage with other ideas with an open-mind and without prejudice or bias. Such an approach will in itself make us more tolerant and accepting of other cultures, beliefs and ideas. The history of Jain logic itself is a testimony to the spirit of engagement heralded by the Jain scholars throughout the journey of Jain discourse. The Jain logicians interacted with other school of thoughts with a pure academic spirit and even wrote commentaries on the texts of the rival schools. Ideas of the other schools were not discarded and derogated but were tolerated and respected by the Jains. Conflicts can be resolved with ease if we can give more importance to the dictum of logic rather than personal prejudices. The same is expressed by Manibhadra who says that-

“I have no bias for Mahavira, and none against Kapila and others. Reasonable words alone are acceptable to me, whosoever they might be”

Therefore, Ethnocentrism; which keeps one's own cultural viewpoint in the centre can be replaced by the Jain logic and its subsequent approach that believes in equal importance of every standpoint and every belief, culture and thought system. The Jain Logic opens up endless possibilities of exploring truth for an individual. It does not expect a person to follow its principles; rather it inspires them to readily accept different perspectives and treat every idea as a potential truth, providing an entirely different way of seeing the world and receiving ideas which clearly provides a counter for ethnocentric beliefs.

The application of Syadvada in our engagements can help us in understanding the opinions and views of others in respect with their perspective and not through our opinions. This will automatically give rise to plurality and receptiveness, proving to be an effective solution for conflicts of ideas and viewpoints.

Multiplicity of Worldviews

Another problem faced by the twenty-first century human society is the extremity creeping into opinions and views. The tendency to see everything in the lens of 'black and white' is caused by extreme standpoints, sharpening ideological differences even more. While the general belief is to view things from the lens of positive and negative, thus; choosing two extremities, the Jain logic holds into view that there exist innumerable worldviews which are different and independent in their own respect. According to the philosophy of Syadvada, every judgment is made in a particular discourse and context and therefore, should be understood in that particular perspective.

The story of the seven blind men popular as 'andhagajanyaya' in Jain discourse should be mentioned here to reflect the present-day problem of extremity in worldview and the Jain idea of relative judgment. A group of blind men heard that a strange animal, called an elephant, had been brought to the town, but none of them were aware its shape and form. Out of curiosity, they said: "We must inspect and know it by touch of which we are capable." So, they sought it out, and when they found it they groped about it. In the case of the first one person, whose hand landed on the trunk, said "This being is like a drain pipe."

For another one whose hand reached its ear, it seemed like a kind of fan. As for another person, whose hand was upon its leg, said, "I perceive the shape of the elephant to be like a pillar." And in the case of the one who placed his hand upon its back said "Indeed, this elephant is like a throne"

Now, each of these presented a true aspect when he related what he had gained from experiencing the elephant. None of them had strayed from the true description of the elephant. Yet they fell short of fathoming the true appearance of the elephant. This example reflects the one-sidedness towards objects in our approach and the subsequent belief of absolutism in that particular viewpoint.

The Jain worldview is opposite to this tendency and believes in multi-faceted nature of reality. This multiplicity of worldviews is expressed in the epistemological structure of 'Saptbhanginaya', which is actually the seven different ways to state an object. These seven viewpoints of 'Saptbhanginaya' are-

1. **Syād-asti**—"in some ways it is"
2. **Syād-nāsti**—"in some ways it is not"
3. **Syād-asti-nāsti**—"in some ways it is and it is not"
4. **Syād-asti-avaktavyaḥ**—"in some ways it is and it is indescribable"
5. **Syād-nāsti-avaktavyaḥ**—"in some ways it is not and it is indescribable"
6. **Syād-asti-nāsti-avaktavyaḥ**—"in some ways it is, it is not and it is indescribable"
7. **Syād-avaktavyaḥ**—"in some ways it is indescribable"

Therefore, the dichotomy of 'affirmative' and 'negative' judgments believed by the modern logic is replaced by a seven-fold methodology of judgment that can occupy contrasting viewpoints at the same time. Even the views which depict the indescribable nature of the object, describe that indescribability from a particular point which means that from some other perspective, the same object can be of a well-defined nature. This also means that a truth which can't be fully perceived has to be accepted with the same affirmativeness, the alternative definitive modes of which are depicted by the last four viewpoints.

Another special feature of the doctrine of Saptbhanginaya is the synthetic approach acquired by it, through which all possible views of truth can be incorporated. This approach accommodates the multiplicity and diversity of viewpoints, enabling reconciliation among all of them. The dispute between Eternalism and Momentarism can also be reconciled through the relative methodology of Saptbhanginaya which can easily accommodate both the worldviews with similar acceptability. Through the epistemological structure of Saptabhanginaya , Jainism balances between idealism and realism and appears as a realist philosophy which is different from all other pragmatic philosophies. These aspects of relativity and co-existence shall be dealt with in a later section. In short, the general tendency to see everything in 'black and white' and to harbor two extreme points can be successfully solved by the idea of Saptbhanginaya and its accommodation of multiple worldviews which has become a need of the hour for developing a sense of plurality and diversity in the society. Through Saptabhanginaya, we can develop a relative viewpoint considering the different ideas as correct from their standpoints without rejecting their presence on the basis of their different locus. This seven-fold epistemological structure can easily accommodate every worldview and will encourage individuals to look beyond what they know or what they perceive, causing a better understanding and engagement in the society.

The Idea of Co-existence

One of the most important requisites for maintaining a peaceful socio-cultural order is the acceptance of co-existence among diverse views and ideologies. The extremity of viewpoints has caused hostility and led to the growing belief that two divergent or polar opinions cannot exist in the same sphere, which becomes disruptive because of the presence of contrasting and divergent opinions in the same sphere.

The doctrine of Anekanta holds the key to solving the existing disruption in social order because of its inherent capability of ensuring co-existence among every sort of idea and ideology. The problem of accommodating contrasting opinions doesn't create an obstacle for the Jain logic for which contrasting

opinions aren't a problem in the first place. The same is expressed by Hemchandra who proudly heralds that the Jain order established by the Arihantas isn't dismantled by contradictions. Amritachandra, a prominent commentator on Kundkunda Samaysara even goes on to say in his commentary on Samaysara that Anekanta is in itself the depiction of two contrasting qualities (Shakti) of an object. The doctrine of Syadvada believes that every tatva is Anekantic by nature. The one which is 'that' is also 'not that', which is 'existent' is also 'non-existent' and which is permanent is also transient. Therefore as Amritachandra propounds, synthesis of contrasting qualities is the basic nature of Anekanta.

Ultimately, the Jain logic is successful in conciliating diametrically divergent dharmas through the doctrines of Naya and Saptabhangi which are integral to Anekanta which give us a relative, synthesizing and non-absolutist approach to look at worldviews. So accepting is Anekantavada of contrasting ideologies that it considers those standpoints as fallacious which do take into consideration their contrasting viewpoints. Hence in the Anekantic system, every thought system or idea is obliged to accept the presence of its contrasting idea along with it. The requirement of this kind of acceptance in the present day time will be automatically very clear to the reader.

The conflict between Eternalism and Momentarism serves as the perfect example of the reconciliation of two contrasting viewpoints. While the Nyaya School took the former position, the Buddhist philosophers championed the latter belief. These two standpoints are visibly polar in nature and are based on two drastically contrasting ideas of the world. Through the relative approach augmented by Nayavada and Saptbhanginaya, the Jain logic arrives a point of conciliation between the two standpoints by mentioning that an object is eternal in the aspect of the continuity of its existence (guna) and is momentary in the aspect of the continuous changes it undergoes in its modes (paryaya). The resultant concept of Utpada-Vyaya-Dhrauvya which is very well depicted through the example of milk and its conversion into curd and the presence of the 'being' of milk in all modes by Vidyanandi in his work 'Ashtasahastri'. This concept of Utpada-Vyaya-Dhrauvya depicts the presence of permanence and transience in the same dravya and was developed through the doctrine of

relativity of Nayavada comprising both the contrasting aspects in an accommodative manner. It is therefore, a remarkable instance of how the Jain logic ensures co-existence of different ideologies.

The Jain logic also developed a peculiar methodology of 'Vivaksha' (implication) for accommodating contrasting viewpoints. Umasvami in his Tattvarthasutra, provides us with the idea of 'Arpita' and 'Anarpita' which when applied on a set of contrasting viewpoints, makes one view as prominent and the other as auxiliary on the basis of the 'Vivaksha' or the implied perspective. Arpita is the prominent dharma and Anarpita is the dharma made secondary. Through this dichotomy, co-existence of two divergent dharmas is proven in the same tattva. This methodology is also based upon 'Nayavada' and operates through considering one perspective as central. Again taking the question of eternalism and momentarism into account, the methodology of 'Arpita-Anarpita' will hold the object eternal and permanent through the perspective of 'Dravyavarthikanayaa' and while making the analogy of 'Paryayarthikanaya' central, it will hold the same object as temporary and momentary. Hence, both the contrasting shaktis of 'Nitya' and 'Anitya' will be proven as co-existing in the same locus.

Another reason behind the ability of the Jain logic to ensure co-existence in the social order is the refutation of absolutism done in its doctrines. The dogmatic idea of absolutism not only disregards other views but is also violent towards them. There is no space for debate or engagement in an absolutist framework, causing the breakdown of harmony. Jain logic, through the doctrine of Syadvada discards absolutism and brings forth the idea of relativity which can uphold social order. Samantbhadra in his Aptamimamsa says-

“Syadvada is the assertion of an entity by some way or the other by discarding absolutism in every respect” (Aptamimamsa. 105)

The relative approach will not only discard absolutism but also encourage people to observe and understand other ideas in their special perspective and form their opinions on the basis of those observations. Such an approach will harbor mutual understanding and respect that will automatically strengthen the ideal of peaceful co-existence. The reconciliatory nature of Jain logic and its

opposition to intellectual dogma should be again mentioned here because of their direct relation with the possibilities of harmonious existence of different views and ideologies.

Counter to One-Sided Viewpoints

Another major problem at the intellectual level which the present day civilization is gripped with is the tendency to remain one sided in viewpoints and ideas. Such tendency refuses to take up other thoughts into considerations and also leads to a bias in the favor of one's own thought system. The Samanvaya sutra mentions the existence of 363 different schools of thoughts being classified in 4 subgroups namely: Kriyavaadi, Akriyavaadi, Gyanvaadi and Agyanvaadi. Every one of these four subgroups based itself on one proposition of never giving a thought to others viewpoint. It is in such scenarios that growth of ideas stagnates and the acceptance of different worldviews stops. In such a scenario, a thought system would lose its relevance because it will no longer be able to include new thoughts and fresh ideas within its thought system. Considering the present time period, many of the problems that individuals face are a result of the one-sided approach they pursue which makes a holistic viewpoint of things impossible.

Jainism is very clear in its outlook regarding the dogma of being one sided. As mentioned earlier, Jain logic considers those standpoints as fallacious which do not consider their contradictions as true. A standpoint has to accept its opposite views as relative truths or else it shall convert into fallacy itself. This concept is very well explained by Hemchandra who explains Durnaya (fallacious Naya) as the one sided absolutist viewpoint-

“When a partial truth is put forward as in the proposition Sat without excluding its contradictory by putting an ‘एव’ is Naya, i.e. Partial Truth. But to say ‘Sadaiva’ (always) and thus exclude the element of Asat is Durnaya. Pramana is a synthesis of Sat and Asat.”

Hence, according to Jainism, fallacy does not lie in the opposing claims of the other views but in the absolutist one-sided claim that only their view is the true one. This is also reflected in the history of Jain logic which didn't have problems with differing views but with the absolutist claims of truth by the other schools

of philosophy. Every school quarrels because it considers its view to be the only truth and does not accept the many-sidedness of the true nature of an object. Hence, Jainism is critical of their one-sided worldview and gives a powerful opposition to this dogma. The idea of Durnaya implies this very fact that a Naya can be true only till it maintains its relativity; the moment it leaves its relativity, it gets converted into Durnaya. The same is with every viewpoint, it will get fallacious only if gets one-sided in its approach. Jain logic doesn't disregard partial knowledge or the knowledge of a particular aspect, it accepts the truth present in every opinion and in every Naya; the only thing it has a problem with is the adamancy that only one fragment or aspect is the entire truth. When a person doesn't accept the partial nature of their knowledge, they get stuck to only a single side of the truth which gets fallacious due to the lack of relativity. This adamancy and lack of acceptance is what Jain logic considers as wrong.

Another phenomenon which is attached with such a one-sided approach is that of being biased as mentioned earlier too. Non-acceptance caused due to an absolutist ideology makes a person partisan towards their belief and hostile towards the other. The same idea is expressed by Haribhadra in his Shaddarshansamucchaya where he says that a person suffering from bias towards his view will mend arguments and logic to suit his own position in any manner. This certainly causes harm to social well being as it obstructs development of new ideas and their enhancement. Hence, Hemchandra says that the Anekantic approach is without any bias because there is no partisanship in its viewpoint. A classical example of this can be seen in the seven Naigam Nayas mentioned in the Tattvarthasutra which present their own viewpoints in regard to their perspectives. The individuals studying them should take them in relative senses and not just limit themselves to one aspect.

Social well being is greatly dependent upon the willingness of the members of the society to listen to other viewpoints and treat them in a relative manner. If they will focus only on one aspect and discard other perspectives, conflicts and discontent will happen in any society or nation because there will be no space for the expression of multiple viewpoints. Therefore, multiplicity of worldviews will lead to positive engagement and holistic approach towards every issue of

the nation and the society. Jainism and its doctrine of Anekanta are fully capable in providing us with such kind of an approach

Importance of All Opinions

The twenty first century can be said as an era of crisis in the realm of human civilization. The reason is that we give so much attention to short-range and local problems that long-range and global problems continue to be neglected. Secondly, life has become more intricately interdependent and complex and hence, simple solutions no longer suffice to the needs of the society. A world civilization is fast emerging and we cannot afford to solve our problems with a parochial temper and sectarian outlook and hence we need cooperation on a plenary scale able to deal with rapidly increasing complexities. The critical problems are so complex that we need a philosophy equally complex to grapple with them. Not only this is too late in history to convert all of mankind to Christianity or Islam or Jainism (or to Communism or Capitalism or any other isms), but also to some metaphysical principles which we have been cherishing since antiquity.

Jain logic is against all kinds of imperialism in ideologies and worldviews. For each community there is a special absolute but the absolutes themselves are alternatives so far as they are probables. One should also remember that this is present only at the level of thought. At the same time, when I have chosen one it is more than possible, it is existent or actual. So there is wonderful reconciliation between what is conditional and what is unconditional. Jain logic believes that everything is conditional on thought level, but on the level of existence there is no real contradiction.

To avoid the fallacy of infinite regress, the Jainas distinguish between valid non-absolutism (Samyak Anekanta) and invalid non-absolutism (Mithya Anekanta). Like an invalid absolute judgment, an invalid non-absolute judgment, too, is invalid. To be valid, Anekanta must not be absolute but relative. If we consider the above points, we cannot say that the “theory of relativity cannot be logically sustained without the hypothesis of an absolute.” Thought is not mere distinction but also relation. Everything is possible only in relation to and as distinct from others and the Law of Identity. Under these circumstances, it is not legitimate to hold that the hypothesis of an absolute cannot be sustained

without the hypothesis of a relative. Absolute to be absolute presupposes a relative somewhere and in some forms, even the relative of its non-existence.

Jaina logic of Anekanta is based not on abstract intellectualism but on experience and realism leading to a non-absolutistic attitude of mind. Multiplicity and unity, definability and non-definability etc. which apparently seem to be contradictory characteristics of reality are interpreted to co-exist in the same object from different points of view without any offence to logic. They seem to be contradictory of each other simply because one of them is mistaken to be the whole truth. In fact, integrity of truth consists in this very variety of its aspects, within the rational unity of an all comprehensive and ramifying principle. The charge of contradiction against the co-presence of being and non-being in the real is figment of a priori logic.

This non-absolutistic attitude of mind which is mentioned above harbors a genuine respect for everyone's opinions and views and accepts contradictions and diversities as truths from the lens of relativity. The present day democratic set up is not only suffering from absolutist egos but also from the anticipation that diverse standpoints cannot survive together. In such an environment, opinions are seen from a view of suspicion making us unable to appreciate every idea and thought. Jainism counters this lack of receptivity by balancing both the absolute and the relative, allowing individuals to be true to their own ideas while appreciating other ideas at the same time. The approach of relativity will also not allow the development of any kind of 'ideological imperialism', providing every worldview a stimulus of growth.

One should also not forget that the doctrines of Naya and Saptabhangi are based upon the possibility of truth in every statement and in every worldview. When these doctrines are implemented upon our interactions, we consider every opinion as a potent relative truth and hence develop sincerity in receiving those opinions. The same is applicable to a democratic system in which no opinion should be discounted or disrespected. When the idea of relative truth propounded by Nayavada shall be applied in democratic functioning, every institution shall be empowered by the amalgamation of every viewpoint and opinion because all of them shall be given their due importance.

Concluding Remarks

The twenty first century has been witnessing the rise of conflicts and hostility which are in a stark contrast to the rapid modernization that has taken place. Nobel Laureate Amartya Sen argues that we are becoming increasingly divided along lines of religion and culture, ignoring the many other ways in which people see themselves, from class and profession to morals and politics. When we are put into narrow categories the importance of human life becomes lost. Through his lucid exploration of such subjects as multiculturalism, fundamentalism, terrorism and globalization, he brings out the need for a clear-headed understanding of human freedom and a constructive public voice in Global civil society. The questions of global peace, sustainable development and welfare of the people can be solved only if we adhere to the ideas of non-absolutism, co-existence and mutual respect. Jain logic which has an essentially pluralistic and relative outlook towards the world and believes in the co-existence of contrasting viewpoints appears as a ray of hope that can make our world order more tolerant, peaceful and devoid of dogmatism. It will be suitable to conclude with the affirmation that the hope of harmony in today's world lies in a clearer understanding of our sheer diversity which is possible only with the adoption of the principle of Anekanta in daily life.

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